

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were *or* Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals. 7%: 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage: Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common not trade – names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing rice variety for irrigated lands

J. S. Nanda, S. C. Mani, H. Singh, and J. P. Singh, Plant Breeding Department, College of Agriculture, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing, dwarf (93 cm) rice variety was released recently in UP for cultivation in irrigated fields. It was developed in Sri Lanka from the cross IR262/Remadja

and tested in the International Rice Observational Nursery as BG90-2 in 1974. The plants have good tillering capacity, mature in 126-132 d, and have high yield potential. Grains are long, slender, and translucent, with good cooking quality. It is moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya, which has become susceptible.

Pant Dhan 4 was tested in station trials from 1976 to 1980 and in state variety trials from 1979 to 1982 (see table). □

Performance of Pant Dhan 4 in state variety trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial center	Grain yield (t/ha)				Days to maturity	
	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya	CD at 5%	CV in %	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya
<i>1981 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	4.6	4.6	0.1	1.8	134	131
Bareilly	7.0	6.7	0.2	2.1	133	141
Haldwani	7.2	5.4	1.2	12.4	139	143
Hardoi	4.1	4.3	0.2	4.3	124	135
Mathura	5.1	4.8	0.3	4.5	123	130
Meerut	2.0	1.7	0.3	12.6	140	141
Jhansi	2.1	2.5	0.6	16.1	123	127
Barabanki	3.2	3.6	0.4	7.9	122	129
Etawah	3.1	4.3	1.0	20.6	122	126
Varanasi	3.1	3.5	1.5	12.0	110	126
Average	4.2	4.2	–	–	126	133
<i>1982 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	3.8	4.5	0.09	1.73	131	133
Bareilly	5.9	5.6	0.07	0.75	132	139
Haldwani	5.8	5.5	0.9	9.8	152	154
Hardoi	4.8	4.7	0.3	5.3	130	138
Mathura	4.3	4.6	0.2	3.2	115	128
Meerut	6.3	4.5	1.0	10.8	139	139
Jhansi	5.6	4.1	n.s.	22.2	129	137
Barabanki	–	–	–	–	–	–
Etawah	–	–	–	–	–	–
Varanasi	–	–	–	–	–	–
Average	5.2	4.9	–	–	132	138

Performance of IR50 during sornavari (summer) season

J. Venkatakrishnan, P. Vivekanandan, K. Neelakantapillai, and D. S. Aaron, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur (CPT) 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

In Tamil Nadu, sornavari is from May to Sep. Short-duration (100-120 d) rice varieties are grown. TKM9 (TKM7/IR8)

Yield characteristics of short-duration varieties at Tirur, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
TKM9	111	450	5.6
IR50	113	415	5.1
ADT36	117	380	5.0
IET4786	118	380	4.6
PY2	108	405	4.5

is popular, but it has short, bold, red grains, and consumers prefer fine-grained, white rice. We tested IR50, with fine white grains, at Tirur.

TKM9, ADT36, PY2, and IET4786

were sown with IR50 on 5 May and transplanted on 6 Jun at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Fifty kg NPK/ha was applied basally before transplanting and 50 kg N/ha was applied in 2 equal splits 15

and 30 d after transplanting.

IR50 yielded less than TKM9 (see table), but it was resistant to mealybug and stem borer. It is becoming popular in sornavari. □

Influence of Zn on distribution and mobility of ⁵⁹Fe in two rice cultivars

C. P. Ghonsikar, D. C. Phulari, D. K. Jadhav, and G. U. Malewar, *Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science Department, Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani 431 402, India*

We evaluated the effect of Zn on distribution and mobility of ⁵⁹Fe on 2 rice cultivars grown on a calcareous Vertisol with pH 8.2, 49.7% clay, 0.62% organic carbon, 0.65 ppm DTPA Zn, 0.5 M NaHCO₃, P₂O₅, 18.5 kg EDTA/ha, and 4.5 ppm Fe.

Two 6-wk-old seedlings of Tuljapur and Jaya were washed with demineralized water and placed in glass bottles with 250 ml of 1/2 strength Hoagland nutrient solution. Zn was added to 5, 10, or 15 µg Zn/ml. 5 µCi/plant of ⁵⁹FeCl₃ in HCl was derived by root absorption, injection into the second internode of plant stems, or smeared on leaf blades. Plants were removed from the bottles on day 6, washed with distilled water, rinsed with 0.1 N HCl, and washed again with distilled water. Roots, stems, and leaves were separated and analyzed. Dried plant samples were digested with a triacid mixture and radioassayed.

Plant parts treated with ⁵⁹Fe retained maximum ⁵⁹Fe within them,

Table 1. Effect of Zn application on distribution or translocation of ⁵⁹Fe in various plant parts of rice cultivars, Parbhani, India.

Application	Zn (kg/ha)	Distribution/translocation of ⁵⁹ Fe (% total activity in rice plant)		
		Root	Stem	Leaf
<i>Tuljapur</i>				
Root	5	56.2	39.5	4.3
	10	49.1	45.2	5.7
	15	52.8	41.1	6.2
Stem	5	41.9	49.5	8.6
	10	46.7	50.4	2.9
	15	37.6	55.3	7.1
Leaf	5	5.4	43.2	51.5
	10	4.0	42.7	53.5
	15	5.9	34.9	59.2
<i>Jaya</i>				
Root	5	58.9	34.5	6.6
	10	53.7	41.2	4.7
	15	53.7	40.4	5.9
Stem	5	43.7	48.3	8.0
	10	46.7	49.6	3.7
	15	38.4	54.8	6.8
Leaf	5	5.7	43.1	51.2
	10	4.6	41.5	53.9
	15	6.4	35.2	58.4

and 41 to 51% was translocated to other plant parts (Table 1). A considerably higher proportion of leaf-smeared than stem-injected ⁵⁹Fe was retained in leaves of both the cultivars. Zn application levels had no consistent effect on ⁵⁹Fe translocations.

Mobility ratios (Table 2) showed that ⁵⁹Fe mobility was greatest in the

Table 2. Effect of Zn application on mobility ratio of ⁵⁹Fe in various parts of rice cultivars, Parbhani, India.

Application	Zn (kg/ha)	Mobility ratio (%)		
		Root	Stem	Leaf
<i>Tuljapur</i>				
Root	5	—	0.7	0.1
	10	—	0.9	0.1
	15	—	0.8	0.1
Stem	5	0.8	—	0.2
	10	0.9	—	0.1
	15	0.7	—	0.1
Leaf	5	0.1	0.8	—
	10	0.1	0.8	—
	15	0.1	0.6	—
<i>Jaya</i>				
Root	5	—	0.6	0.1
	10	—	0.8	0.1
	15	—	0.8	0.1
Stem	5	0.9	—	0.2
	10	0.9	—	0.1
	15	0.7	—	0.1
Leaf	5	0.1	0.8	—
	10	0.1	0.8	—
	15	0.1	0.6	—

stems of rice plants. The stem functioned as a sink for Fe, independent of application method. The two cultivars did not have markedly different Fe translocation patterns.

Studies on ⁵⁹Fe translocation indicate that foliar application of Fe gave better retention in functional or active parts (leaves and stems), and that it may protect against nutrient-induced Fe chlorosis. □

Audiovisual rice production modules

A 43-module series of audiovisual lessons in rice production may be purchased from IRRI. The modules cover seven topic areas: production management; growth and morphology of rice; production problems and techniques; weeds, diseases, and their control; pests and their control; research design and analysis; and soil relationships. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Department, Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.